

On πg_s - λ Closed Sets in Generalized Topological Spaces

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Abstract

In this paper, a new class of generalized closed sets called πg_s - λ closed sets is introduced and some of its properties are studied. Alongwith, the notion of πg_s - λ -continuity and πg_s - λ - $T_{1/2}$ spaces are introduced.

Keywords: generalized topological spaces, g -closed set, π -open set, πg_s - λ closed set

1. Introduction

After the introduction of semi open sets in 1963, Levine [16] also suggested another way of defining the generalized open sets. In 1970, he introduced the notion of g -closed sets [17]. This notion was extensively studied by many topologists. Some of them also suggested several new separation axioms such as $T_{1/2}$, T_{g_s} , πg_p - $T_{1/2}$ and $T_{3/4}$ [8, 12]. Some of these axioms have found their use in quantum physics, computer science and digital topology [8, 14, 9, 19, 15, 10]. Due to its usefulness, the notion of g -closed sets was further investigated in detail. In 1996, Dontchev and Noiri introduced πg -closed sets [8] and used it to obtain a characterization and some preservation theorems for quasi normal spaces. Further, Aslim et. al. defined πg_s -closed sets [11] for topological spaces. It was found that a regular open set can be decomposed into a π -open set and a πg_s -closed set.

In the mean while, in 1997 Császàr [3] introduced a uniform approach to define generalized open sets in topology and accordingly defined *generalized topologies*, which are generalized form of topology. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in research exploring the properties of these structures through the lens of topology and generalized topological frameworks, as evidenced by multiple studies [18, 7, 2, 1, 13]. In this paper, we introduce and study πg_s - λ -closed sets for the generalized topological spaces. We also introduce πg_s - λ -continuity and πg_s - λ -irresoluteness in this process.

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2. Preliminaries

Császàr, using monotonic functions from the family of all subsets of a non empty set X to itself, defined a subfamily λ of $P(X)$, called the family of all λ -open sets and established that λ is a generalized topology [5], i.e., $\emptyset \in \lambda$ and λ is closed under arbitrary union. The complement of a λ -open set is called a λ -closed set. Given a generalized topology λ of subsets of X , the largest λ -open set contained in a subset A of X is called the λ -interior [4] of A and is denoted by $int(A)$. The smallest λ -closed set containing A is called the λ -closure of A and is denoted by $cl(A)$.

A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is g -closed if the closure of A is included in every open superset of A . Through out this paper, spaces (X, λ) and (Y, μ) always mean generalized topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated.

A subset A is said to be λ -regular open (resp. λ -regular closed) if $A = int(cl(A))$ (resp. $A = cl(int(A))$). The finite union of λ -regular open sets is said to be $\pi\lambda$ -open. The complement of a $\pi\lambda$ -open is said to be $\pi\lambda$ -closed. A subset A is said to be λ -semi open [3] if $A \subseteq cl(int(A))$ and the complement of a λ -semi open set is λ -semi closed. The intersection of all λ -semi closed sets containing A is called λ -semi closure of A and is denoted by $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$. Dually the semi interior of A is defined to be the union of all λ -semi open sets contained in A and is denoted by $int_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$. A subset A is said to be $pre\lambda$ -open [3] if $A \subseteq int(cl(A))$ and the complement of a $pre\lambda$ -open set is $pre\lambda$ -closed. The intersection of all $pre\lambda$ -closed sets containing A is called $pre\lambda$ -closure of A and is denoted by $cl_{p(\lambda)}(A)$. Dually the pre interior of A is defined to be the union of all $pre\lambda$ -open sets contained in A and is denoted by $int_{p(\lambda)}(A)$.

Note that for a generalized topological space [6],

$$cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) = A \cup int(cl(A))$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} int_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) &= A \cap cl(int(A)); \\ cl(int(A)) &\subseteq cl_{p(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq cl(A) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$int(A) \subseteq int_{p(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq int(cl(A)).$$

3. $\pi g s \lambda$ -Closed Sets

Definition 3.1. A subset A of a generalized topological space (X, λ) is called

- (i) $g\lambda$ -closed if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is λ -open in X .
- (ii) $\pi g\lambda$ -closed if $cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\pi\lambda$ -open in X .
- (iii) $gp\lambda$ -closed if $cl_{p(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is λ -open in X .
- (iv) $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed if $cl_{p(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\pi\lambda$ -open in X .
- (v) $gs\lambda$ -closed if $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is λ -open in X .
- (vi) $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed if $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is $\pi\lambda$ -open in X .
- (vii) $\pi gs\lambda$ -open (resp. $g\lambda$ -open, $\pi g\lambda$ -open, $gp\lambda$ -open, $\pi gp\lambda$ -open, $gs\lambda$ -open) if the complement of A is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed (resp. $g\lambda$ -closed, $\pi g\lambda$ -closed, $gp\lambda$ -closed, $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed, $gs\lambda$ -closed).

Remark 3.2. Let $M = \bigcup\{U_i : U_i \in \lambda\}$. Then for $A \subseteq X$, if $M \not\subseteq A$, then A is vacuously $g\lambda$ -closed.

Now we have the following relationship:

Theorem 3.3. Let (X, λ) be a generalized topological space, then the relationships amongst various generalized closed sets defined above for a generalized topology can be depicted as follows:

Proof. Obvious. □

Here none of these implications is reversible, as is shown by the following example:

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\lambda = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Here λ is a generalized topology. We have the following:

- (i) $A = \{c, d\}$ is $g\lambda$ -closed set but not λ -closed as $\{a, b\}$ is not λ -open in (X, λ) .
- (ii) $A = \{b, c\}$ is λ -semi closed but not λ -closed in X .
- (iii) $A = \{a, d\}$ is $pre\lambda$ -closed but not λ -closed in X .
- (iv) $A = \{a, c, d\}$ is $gp\lambda$ -closed and $gs\lambda$ -closed but not $pre\lambda$ -closed and not λ -semi closed.
- (v) $A = \{c\}$ is $gp\lambda$ -closed set but not $g\lambda$ -closed as $A \subseteq \{b, c\}$, an λ -open set in X .
- (vi) $A = \{b\}$ is $gs\lambda$ -closed set but not $g\lambda$ -closed as $A \subseteq \{b, c\}$, an λ -open set in X .
- (vii) $A = \{a\}$ is $gs\lambda$ -closed set but not $gp\lambda$ -closed.
- (viii) $A = \{c\}$ is $gp\lambda$ -closed set but not $gs\lambda$ -closed.
- (ix) $A = \{b\}$ is $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed set but not $g\lambda$ -closed.
- (x) $A = \{c\}$ is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed set but not $gs\lambda$ -closed.
- (xi) $A = \{b, c\}$ is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed set but not $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed nor $\pi g\lambda$ -closed.

Finally, $\{c\}$ is $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed but not $\pi g\lambda$ -closed.

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\lambda = \{\emptyset, X, \{b, c\}, \{b, d\}, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Here λ is a generalized topology. We have the following:

- (i) $A = \{c\}$ is $\pi g\lambda$ -closed set but not $g\lambda$ -closed.
- (ii) $A = \{b, c\}$ is $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed set but not $gp\lambda$ -closed.

Theorem 3.6. For a subset $A \subseteq X$, the following conditions are equivalent:

- (i) A is $\pi\lambda$ -open and $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed.

(ii) A is λ -regular open.

Proof. (i) \implies (ii): A is $\pi\lambda$ -open and $A \subseteq A$. Therefore $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq A$ as A is $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed. Therefore $int(cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Also A is λ -open. Hence A is pre λ -open also, that is $A \subseteq int(cl(A))$. Thus $A = int(cl(A))$, that is, A is λ -regular open.

(ii) \implies (i): Let A is λ -regular open then A is $\pi\lambda$ -open. Also, $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) = A \cup int(cl(A)) = A$ and hence A is $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed as well. □

Theorem 3.7. If A is $\pi\lambda$ -open and $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed, then A is λ -semi closed and hence $g s \lambda$ -closed.

Proof. By the Theorem 3.6, we have A is λ -regular open. Therefore A is λ -semi closed. Hence $int(cl(A)) \subseteq A$. Since every λ -semi closed set is $g s \lambda$ -closed. Hence A is $g s \lambda$ -closed. □

Corollary 3.8. If A is $\pi\lambda$ -open and $\pi g p \lambda$ -closed then A is λ -regular closed. Hence A is $\pi\lambda$ -closed.

Proof. Let A be $\pi\lambda$ -open and $\pi g p \lambda$ -closed. Thus $cl_{p(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq A$, therefore $cl(int(A)) \subseteq A$. As A is λ -open, it is λ -semi open in X also. Thus $A \subseteq cl(int(A))$. Hence $A = cl(int(A))$, A is λ -regular closed, thus $\pi\lambda$ -closed. □

Remark 3.9. We can conclude that if A is $\pi\lambda$ -open, then the following are equivalent:

1. A is $\pi\lambda$ -closed;
2. A is λ -closed;
3. A is pre λ -closed;
4. A is $g p \lambda$ -closed;
5. A is $\pi g p \lambda$ -closed;
6. A is $g \lambda$ -closed;
7. A is $\pi g \lambda$ -closed;

Remark 3.10. Union of two $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed (resp. $\pi g p \lambda$ -closed) sets need not be $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed (resp. $\pi g p \lambda$ -closed) set.

Example 3.11. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\lambda = \{\emptyset, X, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}\}$. Here λ is a generalized topology. The sets $A = \{a\}$, and $B = \{b, c\}$ both are $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed but $A \cup B = \{a, b, c\}$ is not $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed. Similarly, $C = \{b\}$, and $D = \{c\}$ both are $\pi g p \lambda$ -closed but $C \cup D = \{b, c\}$ is not a $\pi g p \lambda$ -closed set.

Remark 3.12. Intersection of two $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed sets need not be $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed.

Example 3.13. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ with $\lambda = \{\emptyset, X, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{b, c, d\}\}$. Then $A = \{b, c, d\}$ and $B = \{a, c, d\}$ both are $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed. But $A \cap B = \{c, d\}$ is not $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed.

In the following we derive a sufficient condition for the union of two $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed sets to be $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed. Here a λ -semi limit point refers to a semi limit point with respect to the generalized topology λ on X .

Definition 3.14. Let (X, λ) be a *generalized topological space* and $A \subseteq X$. Then the set of all λ -semi limit points of A is called the λ -semi derived set of A and is denoted by $D_{\sigma(\lambda)}[A]$.

Similarly $x \in D_{\lambda}[A]$ if and only if any λ -open set U such that $x \in U$ meets $A \setminus \{x\}$.

Theorem 3.15. Let A and B be $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed sets in (X, λ) such that $D_{\lambda}[A] \subseteq D_{\sigma(\lambda)}[A]$ and $D_{\lambda}[B] \subseteq D_{\sigma(\lambda)}[B]$, then $A \cup B$ is $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed.

Proof. For any set $E \subseteq X$, $D_{\sigma(\lambda)}[E] \subseteq D_{\lambda}[E]$, as every λ -open set is λ -semi open set. Therefore $D[A] = D_{\sigma(\lambda)}[A]$, $D[B] = D_{\sigma(\lambda)}[B]$, that is $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) = cl(A)$ and $cl(B) = cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(B)$.

Let $A \cup B \subseteq U$, where U be a $\pi\lambda$ -open set in X . Then $A \subseteq U, B \subseteq U$. Thus we get $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A \cup B) \subseteq cl(A \cup B) = cl(A) \cup cl(B) = cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \cup cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(B) \subseteq U$, as A, B are $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed. Hence $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A \cup B) \subseteq U$. Thus $A \cup B$ is $\pi g s \lambda$ -closed. □

Remark 3.16. As in above theorem, we can also show that if A and B are $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed (resp. $gp\lambda$ -closed) sets in (X, λ) such that $D_\lambda[A] = D_{p(\lambda)}[A]$ and $D_\lambda[B] = D_{p(\lambda)}[B]$, then $A \cup B$ is $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed (resp. $gp\lambda$ -closed).

Theorem 3.17. Let A is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed and $A \subseteq B \subseteq cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$, then B is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed.

Proof. Let U be any $\pi\lambda$ -open set in X such that $B \subseteq U$, then $A \subseteq B \subseteq U$. Since A is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed set, we have, $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq U$ so that $B \subseteq cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$. This implies $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(B) \subseteq cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$. Hence $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(B) \subseteq U$ as well. Hence B is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed. □

Theorem 3.18. Let A be a $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed set in X , then there is no non empty $\pi\lambda$ -closed set contained in $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \setminus A$.

Proof. Let if possible, F be a non empty $\pi\lambda$ -closed set such that $F \subseteq cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \setminus A \subseteq X \setminus A$. This implies that $A \subseteq X \setminus F$. Now A is a $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed set in X and $X \setminus F$ is $\pi\lambda$ -open set containing A . Thus $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq X \setminus F$ and hence $F \subseteq X \setminus cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$. Therefore $F \subseteq (X \setminus cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)) \cap cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) = \emptyset$. This shows that our assumption was wrong. □

4. $\pi gs\lambda$ -Continuity and $\pi gs\lambda$ -Irresoluteness

Definition 4.1. Let $(X, \lambda), (Y, \mu)$ be two generalized topological space. A function $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$ is called $\pi gs(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed in (X, λ) , for every μ -closed set V in (Y, μ) .

Definition 4.2. Let $(X, \lambda), (Y, \mu)$ be two generalized topological space, A function $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$ is said to be

- (i) $\pi(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous (respectively $\pi g(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous, $\pi gp(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous) if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\lambda$ -closed (respectively $\pi g\lambda$ -closed, $\pi gp\lambda$ -closed) in (X, λ) for every μ -closed set V in (Y, μ) .
- (ii) (λ, μ) semi continuous (respectively $g(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous, $gs(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous) if $f^{-1}(V)$ is λ -semi closed (respectively $g\lambda$ -closed, $gs\lambda$ -closed) in (X, λ) for every μ -closed set V in (Y, μ) .
- (iii) $\pi(\lambda, \mu)$ irresolute if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi\lambda$ -closed in (X, λ) for every $\pi\mu$ -closed set V in (Y, μ) .
- (iv) (λ, μ) regular open if $f^{-1}(V)$ is λ -regular open in (X, λ) for every μ -open set V in (Y, μ) .
- (v) (λ, μ) irresolute if $f^{-1}(V)$ is λ -semi closed in (X, λ) for every μ -semi closed set V in (Y, μ) .

Definition 4.3. Let $(X, \lambda), (Y, \mu)$ be two generalized topological space, then a function $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$ is called $\pi gs(\lambda, \mu)$ irresolute if $f^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed in (X, λ) , for every $\pi gs\mu$ -closed set V in (Y, μ) .

Theorem 4.4. For a map $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$, the following implications hold:

Proof. The results are immediate, in view of Theorem 3.3 □

Remark 4.5. The following examples show that

- (i) $\pi gs(\lambda, \mu)$ continuity need not imply $gs(\lambda, \mu)$ or $\pi g(\lambda, \mu)$ continuity.
- (ii) $\pi gs(\lambda, \mu)$ continuity is independent of $\pi gp(\lambda, \mu)$ continuity

Example 4.6. Let (X, λ) be the same GT as in Example 3.5. Let $Y = \{x, y\}$ and $\mu = \{\emptyset, \{x\}\}$. Define a function $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$ as follows: $f(a) = f(d) = x$, $f(b) = f(c) = y$. Then f is $\pi gs(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous which is neither $\pi gp(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous nor $\pi g(\lambda, \mu)$ continuous.

Theorem 4.7. If $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$ is an (λ, μ) -irresolute regular open bijection, then f is $\pi gs(\lambda, \mu)$ irresolute.

Proof. Let F be any $\pi gs\mu$ -closed set in Y and U be a $\pi\lambda$ -open set in X containing $f^{-1}(F)$. Since f is regular open, therefore $f(U)$ is $\pi\mu$ -open in Y and $F \subseteq f(U)$. Since F is $\pi gs\mu$ -closed set and $f(U)$ is $\pi\mu$ -open. Therefore $cl_{\sigma(\mu)}(F) \subseteq f(U)$, and hence $f^{-1}(cl_{\sigma(\mu)}(F)) \subseteq U$. Since f is (λ, μ) irresolute, therefore $f^{-1}(cl_{\sigma(\mu)}(F))$ is λ -semi closed. Hence $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(f^{-1}(F)) \subseteq cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}[f^{-1}(cl_{\sigma(\mu)}(F))] = f^{-1}(cl_{\sigma(\mu)}(F)) \subseteq U$. Therefore $f^{-1}(F)$ is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed in X , hence f is $(\lambda, \mu)\pi gs$ irresolute. \square

Definition 4.8. A space (X, λ) is called $\pi gs\lambda$ - $T_{1/2}$ space if every $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed set is λ -semi closed.

Theorem 4.9. A space (X, λ) is a $\pi gs\lambda$ - $T_{1/2}$ space if and only if every singleton is either $\pi\lambda$ -closed or λ -semi open.

Proof. Let $x \in X$ and assume that $\{x\}$ is not $\pi\lambda$ -closed. Then clearly $X \setminus \{x\}$ is not $\pi\lambda$ -open. Hence $X \setminus \{x\}$ is trivially $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed. Since (X, λ) is $\pi gs\lambda$ - $T_{1/2}$ space, $X \setminus \{x\}$ is λ -semi closed. Therefore $\{x\}$ is λ -semi open.

Conversely, Let $A \subseteq X$ be $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed and $x \in cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$. We will show that $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq A$.

Consider the following cases:

- Case 1. The set $\{x\}$ is $\pi\lambda$ -closed, then if $x \notin A$, then $A \subseteq X \setminus \{x\}$, which is $\pi\lambda$ -open, Since A is $\pi gs\lambda$ -closed, therefore $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq X \setminus \{x\}$, that is, $x \notin cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$, which leads to a contradiction. Hence $x \in A$.
- Case 2. If the set $\{x\}$ is λ -semi open, $x \in cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A)$. Then $\{x\} \cap A \neq \emptyset$. Thus $x \in A$.

Therefore, in both cases, $x \in A$, that is, $cl_{\sigma(\lambda)}(A) \subseteq A$. This proves that A is λ -semi closed. \square

The notion of $\pi gs\lambda$ - $T_{1/2}$ spaces are different from $T_{1/2}$ spaces.

Example 4.10. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ with GT $\lambda = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{a\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then (X, λ) is a $\pi gs\lambda$ - $T_{1/2}$ space. But it is not a $T_{1/2}$ space as $A = \{a\}$ is a $g\lambda$ -closed set not a closed set.

Remark 4.11. For a map $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$, where X is $\pi gs\lambda$ - $T_{1/2}$ space, then $\pi gs(\lambda, \mu)$ continuity, $gs(\lambda, \mu)$ continuity and (λ, μ) semi continuity all coincide. This follows in the view of Theorem 4.9.

Theorem 4.12. Let $f : (X, \lambda) \rightarrow (Y, \mu)$ and $g : (Y, \mu) \rightarrow (Z, \eta)$ be any two functions, then

- (i) gof is πgs -continuous if g is continuous and f is πgs -continuous.
- (ii) gof is πgs -irresolute if g and f both are πgs -irresolute.
- (iii) gof is πgs -continuous if g is πgs -continuous and f is πgs -irresolute.

Proof. (i) Let V be any η -closed set in Z , then $g^{-1}(V)$ is closed in Y as g is continuous, and πgs -continuity of f implies that $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is πgs -closed in X . Thus gof is πgs -continuous.

(ii) Let V be πgs -closed in (Z, η) , then $g^{-1}(V)$ is again πgs -closed in (Y, μ) as g is πgs -irresolute, and f is also πgs -irresolute, therefore $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V)) = (gof)^{-1}(V)$ is πgs -closed in (X, λ) . Hence gof is πgs -irresolute.

(iii) Let V be η -closed in (Z, η) , g is πgs -continuous then $g^{-1}(V)$ is πgs -closed in (Y, μ) . f is πgs -irresolute, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is πgs -closed in (X, λ) . Hence gof is πgs -continuous. \square

Theorem 4.13. Let $f : (X, \lambda) \longrightarrow (Y, \mu)$ and $f : (Y, \eta) \longrightarrow (Z, \eta)$ be any two maps, and Y is $\pi g s \mu - T_{1/2}$ space, then gof is semi continuous, if f is irresolute and g is $\pi g s$ -continuous.

Proof. Let V be η -closed set in (Z, η) , then $g^{-1}(V)$ is $\pi g s$ -closed in Y , Since g is $\pi g s$ -continuous. (Y, μ) is $\pi g s \mu - T_{1/2}$ space, then $g^{-1}(V)$ is semi closed. Therefore the irresoluteness of f implies that $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(V))$ is semi closed in X . Hence gof is semi continuous. \square

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